

The influence of mother's attitude on neonate visits in the working area of Lambale health center, North Buton district, Southeast Sulawesi Province, Indonesia

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Abstract

Neonatal visits are basic health services provided for neonates at least 3 times, namely 1st neonatal visit at 6 hours to 48 hours after birth, 2nd neonatal visit on days 3 to 7 days, 3rd neonatal visit on days 8 – 28 days. The aim of the study was to determine the effect of respondents' attitudes on neonatal visits in the working area of the Lambale Health Center, North Buton Regency. This type of survey research uses a cross sectional study approach. The research population is 144 people, the sample is 105 people. Data collection was carried out using questionnaires and interviews. Data analysis was performed using univariate and bivariate. The results showed that there was a significant influence on the attitude of the respondents towards neonatal visits, with a p value = 0.000.

Conclusion; There is an influence on the mother's attitude towards neonatal visits in the working area of the Lambale Health Center, North Buton Regency in 2022. Suggestion; Health workers and health cadres are expected to maximize education regarding the importance of neonatal visits after mothers give

Keywords: Neonates; Attitude; Neonatal visits; Survey; Mother's attitude

1. Introduction

Neonates are the first period of life outside the womb up to the age of 28 days [1, 2]. During this period there was a very big change from life which was initially in the womb totally dependent on the mother to outside the womb which had to live independently. During this period there was organ maturation in almost all systems [3]. Babies who are less than one month old have the highest risk of health problems, various health problems can arise so that without proper treatment, they can be fatal.

In 2015, it was reported that the number of under-five deaths in the world was 5.9 million and 2.7 million died during the neonatal period [4]. Neonatal mortality has contributed to infant mortality by 59% at the age of 0-28 days. In 2020, of 28,158 under-five deaths, 72.0% (20,266 deaths) of them occurred during the neonatal period. Of all reported neonatal deaths, 72.0% (20,266 deaths) occurred at the age of 0-28 days, while 19.1% (5,386 deaths) occurred at the age of 29 days – 11 months and 9.9% (2,506 deaths) occurs at the age of 12 – 59 months [5].

The neonatal mortality rate in Southeast Sulawesi in 2019 was 336 and increased to 354 cases (7 per 1000 live births) in 2020 (7 per 1000 live births) [5]. Health profile data for North Buton Regency in 2020 stated that the infant mortality rate in North Buton Regency was 19 cases, an increase compared to 2018 which was only 15 cases [6].

Based on the results of the 2017 Indonesian Demographic and Health Survey, it shows that there has been a decline. Neonatal mortality fell from 19 per 1000 live births in 2012 to 15 per 1000 live births in 2017 [7]. Of all neonatal deaths

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reported in Indonesia in 2020, 72.0% (20,266 deaths) occurred at the age of 0-28 days. Meanwhile, 19.1% (5,386 deaths) occurred at the age of 29 days – 11 months and 9.9% (2,506 deaths) occurred at the age of 12 – 59 months [8].

The 2015-2019 National Medium-Term Development Plan targets to reduce the infant mortality rate per 1,000 live births to 24 in 2019. In addition, the Sustainable Development Goals in the health and welfare sector (SDGs 3), has a target to be achieved in 2030. Target These include ending preventable infant and under-five mortality by reducing the neonatal mortality rate to 12 per 1,000 live births and the under-five mortality rate to 25 per 1,000 live births [9].

Nationally, the first neonatal visit rate (6-48 hours after birth) in 2013 was 71.3% and increased to 84.1% in 2018, where the province with the highest neonatal visit rate was the Special Region of Yogyakarta, namely 95.9%. and the lowest is Papua at 46.2% while for Southeast Sulawesi Province it is still below 80% [10] and in 2020 this number of visits will increase to 94.31%. Specifically for North Buton Regency at 90.77% [6].

Data on neonatal visits to the Public health center according to data from the North Buton District Health Office for 2020, of the 10 existing Public health center, complete neonatal visits at the Lambale Health Center were the lowest, where in the last 3 years it showed a decline, namely in 2018 it was 83.3% then decreased to 74, 9% in 2019 and continues to decrease in 2020 to 71.9% [11]. This shows that neonatal visits are still very low.

Factors related to neonatal visits that affect a person's behavior consist of the first is predisposing factors, which include work, education, parity, knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, family support, adherence to antenatal care visits, beliefs, values, social culture and etc. Researchers are interested in conducting a study of one of the predisposing factors for neonatal visits, namely attitude.

2. Material and methods

This type of survey research uses a *cross sectional study*. This research was conducted in the working area of the Lambale Health Center in September - October 2022. The population in the study, all mothers of babies born in the working area of the Lambale Health Center, North Buton Regency, were 144 people. The size of the research sample used was 105 people. This study uses primary data and secondary data. Data were analyzed by univariate and bivariate.

3. Results

3.1. Univariate Analysis

3.1.1. Attitudes

Attitudes are opinions or assessments of people or respondents on matters related to health, health-illness and factors related to health risk factors. The distribution of respondents according to mother's attitude towards neonatal visits in the Lambale Health Center work area is presented in table 1.

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents according to Mother's Attitudes towards neonatal visits in the Lambale Health Center Working Area in 2022

No	Mother's Attitude	Total (N)	Percentage (%)
1	Negative	39	37
2	Positive	66	63
Total		105	100

Source: Primary data for 2022.

Based on Table 1, it shows that out of 105 respondents (100%), mothers who had a more positive attitude were 66 respondents (63%) compared to mothers who have a negative attitude as many as 39 respondents (37%).

3.1.2. Neonatal visit

Neonatal visits are visits by mothers under five to get neonates services according to standards provided by health workers to neonates, at least 3 visits during the period 0-28 days after birth, both at health facilities and home visits, the 1st Neonatal Visit period is carried out during within 6-48 hours after birth, the 2nd Neonatal Visit was carried out within 3-7 days after birth, the 3rd Neonatal Visit was carried out within 828 days after birth. The distribution of respondents according to the mother's attitude towards neonatal visits in the working area of the Lambale Health Center is presented in table 2.

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents according to Visits of Neonatal Mothers in the Work Area of the Lambale Health Center in 2022

No	Neonatal Visits	Total (N)	Percentage (%)
1	No Complete	78	74
2	Complete	27	26
Total		105	100

Source: Primary data for 2022.

Based on Table 2, it shows that out of 105 respondents (100%), more mothers had incomplete neonatal visits, namely 78 respondents (74%) compared to with mothers who had complete neonatal visits as many as 27 respondents (26%).

3.2. Bivariate Analysis

The Effect of Mother's Attitude on Neonatal Visits in the Lambale Health Center work area

The influence of the mother's attitude towards neonatal visits in the Lambale Health Center work area is presented in Table 3.

Table 3 The Effect of Mother's Attitude on Neonate Visits in the Lambale Health Center working area in 2022

Mother's Attitude	Center				Health		P-value
	Incomplete		Complete		N	(%)	
	n	(%)	n	(%)			
Negative	39	100	0	0	39	100	0.000
Positive	39	59	27	41	66	100	
Total	78	74	27	26	105	100	

Source: Primary data for 2022.

Table 3 showed that of the 39 respondents (100%) mothers who had a negative attitude, there were 39 respondents (100%) mothers who had incomplete neonatal visits. Meanwhile, from 66 respondents (100%) mothers who had a positive attitude had more incomplete neonatal visits, namely 39 respondents (59%) compared to mothers who had a positive attitude with complete neonatal visits, namely 27 respondents (41%)

Chi square test results the value of $p = 0.000$ ($p > 0.05$) means that H_0 is accepted. This shows that there is a significant influence between the attitudes of mothers under five and neonatal visits in the work area of the Lambale Health Center in

4. Discussion

Attitude is how the opinion or assessment of people or respondents to matters related to health, health and illness and factors related to health risk factors. Attitude is also a kind of readiness to react to an object in certain ways. This study showed that the proportion of mothers' attitudes was more positive as many as 66 people (63%) and at least a negative attitude as many as 39 people (37%).

The mother's positive attitude but not carrying out a complete neonatal visit indicates that the mother has high confidence in caring for her own baby at home. This affected his neonatal visits. The self-confidence obtained from the educational history of the respondents, most of whom had a high school graduation educational background.

In addition, it is also influenced by cultural background and experience. The large number of mothers in the working area of the Lambale Health Center who have high parity is influenced by cultural background. The cultural background that influences parity, among others, is the notion that the more children, the more fortune. High parity is also used as a reference for experience so far.

The results of the bivariate test showed that the p value = 0.000 (p value < 0.05), which means that there is an influence between maternal attitudes and neonatal visits in the working area of the Lambale Health Center, West Kulisusu District, North Buton Regency in 2022.

The attitude of the mother regarding neonatal visits in the working area of the Lambale Health Center shows positive things. Mothers who have a positive attitude towards neonatal visits are because the mother has a good understanding of the benefits of these neonatal visits. Vice versa, there are mothers who still have a negative attitude regarding neonatal visits at the Lambale Health Center. This is because mothers do not have a good understanding of neonatal visits, namely they do not routinely carry out ANC, and minimal family support.

Statements of positive and negative attitudes are also influenced by several things, namely personal experience, culture, mass media, education possessed and emotions possessed. The personal experiences we have had and are currently experiencing shape and influence our attitudes. The culture that we have in the environment where we live and are raised has a big influence on the formation of the attitude we will take. The mass media has a major influence in forming one's opinions and beliefs. Owned education also has an influence in the formation of attitudes because of the moral concept within the individual. And not only that, a form of attitude is a statement based on emotion that functions as a kind of channeling frustration or diverting the form of an ego defense mechanism [12].

The attitude statement is a series of sentences that say something about the attitude object to be expressed. The attitude statement may contain or say positive things about the attitude object, namely the sentence supports or is in favor of the attitude object. This statement is called a favorable statement. Conversely, an attitude statement may also contain things that are negative about the attitude object that are neither supportive nor contra to the attitude object [13, 14].

Thus the statements presented are not all positive and not all negative which can give the impression as if the contents of the scale in question are entirely in favor or vice versa wholly do not support the attitude object. Variations *unfavorable* and *statements* will make respondents think more carefully about the contents of their statements before giving a response so that respondent stereotypes in answering can be avoided [15].

Even so, attitude is not a behavior or action, but is a predisposition to behavioral action. Attitude can also be referred to as a person's closed reaction to an object which can include feelings of support or partiality or feelings of not supporting or rejecting an object [16, 17].

A mother thinks that if she brings the baby to the health worker, the baby will be injected and this will make the baby have a fever. A mother thinks that neonatal visits are not necessary because bringing a baby at less than one month of age will endanger her baby so that neonatal visits are not important. A mother also thinks that making neonatal visits is very troublesome and takes a long time [16].

This study is the same as that of Afifah et al., (2013), the attitude variable shows that most postnatal mothers are included in the positive/supportive category for neonatal visits of 57.5% [17]. This study is in line with Zuraida's research (2018), which states that there is a relationship between attitude ($p = 0.004$) and neonatal visits [16].

This research is not in line with the research of Rahmawati et al., (2019) which showed that the majority of respondents had a supportive attitude during neonatal visits (66.7%) [18]. The results of hypothesis testing with *Chi-Square* obtained a p -value of $0.164 \geq 0.05$, which means that there is no relationship between attitudes towards neonatal visits

5. Conclusion

Conclusion; there is an influence on the mother's attitude towards neonatal visits in the work area of the Lambale Health Center with a p value = 0.000. Suggestion; it is hoped that health workers and health cadres will maximize education related to the importance of neonatal visits after mothers give birth.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors in the making of this scientific article have no conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

This research does not give treatment to humans, but is a survey research.

Statement of informed consent

All informants/respondents involved in this study have stated their consent as informants/respondents to be interviewed and provided information/information in accordance with research needs.

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